

Kinetics and mechanistic study of acid-catalysed hydrolysis of *p*-chlorophenyl-2-furohydroxamic acid

Surendra K. Rajput* and Vinita Raghavan

Department of Chemistry, Govt. College of Science, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : vinita_1750@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : The rate of hydrolysis of *p*-chlorophenyl-2-furohydroxamic acid [4-Cl-C₆H₄N(OH)-C(O)-C₄H₃O] has been studied over a wide range of acidities in hydrochloric, sulphuric and perchloric acids in 20% (v/v) dioxane-water at 55 °C. The kinetics has been analysed by Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen and Cox-Yates excess acidity treatments. Solvent, salt and temperature effects has also been probed. The mechanism of acid-catalysed hydrolysis is postulated as involving two steps : a rapid protonation and a rate-determining A-2 nucleophilic attack by water.

Keywords : Acid hydrolysis, heterocyclic acid, rate-acidity correlation.

Continuing our study on hydrolysis of unsubstituted and *N*-substituted heterocyclic hydroxamic acids¹ in acidic medium, we report herein hydrolysis of *p*-chlorophenyl-2-furohydroxamic acid [4-Cl-C₆H₄N(OH)-C(O)-C₄H₃O] in mineral acids. Recently, the excess acidity method developed as a tool for the elucidation of reaction mechanisms in strong acid media, was applied to rate data².

Experimental

p-Chlorophenyl-2-furohydroxamic acid was prepared by standard method³. The acids used were of analytical reagent quality and their concentrations were determined by titrations with standard alkali. Dioxane (B.D.H., A.R.) was used without further purification. Ferric chloride solution used in the colorimetric procedure was prepared by dissolution of 44.0 g of anhydrous ferric chloride (Qualigen, A.R.) in 1 litre distilled water containing 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Kinetic measurements were made by the use of spectrophotometric method reported previously employing UV-Vis 106 Systronics spectrophotometer set at 540 nm⁴.

Results and discussion

The acidic hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA is of first order both in substrate and catalyst, viz. acid, but as the hydrolysis was carried out in excess hydronium ion, pseudo-first order rates were ensured. The rate of

hydrolysis passes through a maximum in all the mineral acids (Table 1). This is attributed to two opposing effects of increasing the acid concentration. On one hand increased acidity raises the concentration of the reactive conjugate acid form of the substrate, and at the same time activity of water needed for complete hydrolysis decreases. This is true only for A-2 hydrolysis, since in A-1 reactions water does not intervene during the rate limiting step.

The order of relative rate of hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA at acid concentration in the range 0.75 to 3.50 *M* is HClO₄

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the hydrolysis of 4-chlorophenyl-2-furohydroxamic acids
Temp. = 55 °C, solvent : 20% (v/v) 1-4 dioxane

Concentration [<i>M</i>]	<i>k_ψ</i> × 10 ⁴ (min ⁻¹)		
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	HClO ₄
0.75	3.25	3.07	13.64
1.45	5.87	5.78	15.92
2.90	13.30	16.29	21.50
3.50	16.07	23.48	23.96
4.50	21.05	35.77	26.52
5.00	25.22	39.22	21.65
5.80	29.51	47.71	17.01
6.50	32.12	49.73	29.48
7.54	30.15	21.96	^a
8.50	32.20	28.51	-

^aHigher perchloric acid concentrations bring about uncontrolled reactions (destruction).

> H₂SO₄ > HCl. At acid concentrations above 3.50 M, the catalytic effectiveness of acid decreases in the sequence H₂SO₄ > HCl > HClO₄.

Activation parameters were also determined for some of the acid solutions (Table 2). These values are not substantially different from those obtained for an ester and amide hydrolysis according to an A-2 mechanism. Therefore, we conclude that the hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA proceeds via a rate-determining attack of water on the protonated substrate, with formation of a tetrahedral intermediate that rapidly breaks down to products. No evidence for a unimolecular pathway, such as changes in activation entropies, was seen for the hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA in the acidity range studied.

Rate-acidity correlations :

Bunnett (ω)⁵, Bunnett-Olsen (ϕ)⁶ and Cox-Yates excess acidity plots² were carried out on the data in Table 1. The results of analysis of the kinetic data in terms of various criteria are shown in Table 3. Bunnett (ω) plots (Fig. 1) of $\log k_{\psi} + H_A$ versus $\log a_w$ were linear with slopes (ω values) in the range 1.8 to 3.3 for all three acids used. Such values of (ω) fall into the range normally associated with water acting as a nucleophile. The plots (Fig. 2) of $\log k_{\psi} + H_A$ versus $\log [H^+] + H_A$ for Bunnett-Olsen treatment gave (ϕ) values in range 1.0 to

1.5. Such (ϕ) values lie in the range said to be characterised of water acting as a proton transfer agent. It is interesting to note that the values of both (ω) and (ϕ) were consistent with water playing an additional role beyond that of a nucleophile.

The Cox-Yates method is capable of revealing mechanistic features which other methods of analysing kinetic data in strong acid cannot. We employed this method to test for an A-2 mechanism. Eq. (1) have been derived for A-2 reactions.

$$\log k_{\psi} - \log C_{H^+} - 2 \log a_w = (\log K_1/K_{SH^+}) + m_2^{\#} m^* x \quad (1)$$

where m^* is obtained from protonation studies, $m_2^{\#}$ is characteristic of the type of reaction, and $\log a_w$ for the A-2 reaction represents nucleophilic activity and is commonly equivalent to $2 \log a_w$, where two water molecules are involved in forming the transition state. The m^* for carbonyl oxygen protonation is 0.6 or less and $m_2^{\#}$ for A-2 reactions is ≈ 1 , thus an overall slope against X of 0.6 or less should result¹⁶ for eq. (1). Good linear plots were obtained (Fig. 3) with slopes in the range 0.28 to 0.63 characteristic of an A-2 process. For these correlations values of H_A and a_w determined at 25 °C and in aqueous medium were used whilst the reaction

Table 2. Activation parameters for the hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA

Concentration [M]	HCl				H ₂ SO ₄				HClO ₄			
	E_a	$\Delta H^{\#}$	$\Delta G^{\#}$	$\Delta S^{\#}$	E_a	$\Delta H^{\#}$	$\Delta G^{\#}$	$\Delta S^{\#}$	E_a	$\Delta H^{\#}$	$\Delta G^{\#}$	$\Delta S^{\#}$
0.75	91.8	89.0	110.9	-66.8	75.1	72.4	111.1	-117.9	78.0	75.3	107.0	-96.8
2.90	67.3	64.6	107.1	-129.7	69.8	67.1	106.6	-120.3	62.8	60.0	105.8	-139.5
5.80	62.3	59.6	104.9	-138.3	63.4	60.7	103.6	-130.8	70.1	67.3	106.4	-119.2

E_a , $\Delta H^{\#}$, $\Delta G^{\#}$ in kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S^{\#}$ in J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹.

Table 3. Rate correlations for the hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA

Correlation	Acid	Slope	Correlation coefficient
Bunnett (ω)	HCl	3.26	0.995
	H ₂ SO ₄	1.82	0.986
	HClO ₄	2.62	0.994
Bunnett-Olsen (ϕ)	HCl	1.01	0.996
	H ₂ SO ₄	1.01	0.962
	HClO ₄	1.47	0.974
Cox-Yates excess acidity ($m_2^{\#} m^*$)	HCl	0.40	0.997
	H ₂ SO ₄	0.63	0.889
	HClO ₄	0.28	0.919

were carried out at 55 °C and this might affect the magnitudes of the slopes.

Salt effect : Many added salts increase the protonating power of the medium, as measured by acidity function and therefore, generally assist acid hydrolysis. The salt effect of perchlorates is negligible or slightly negative in A-2 acid catalysed hydrolysis of esters, whereas chlorides assist the hydrolysis slightly⁷.

The rate of hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA was studied in hydrochloric acid (1.45 M) using NaCl, KCl and LiCl. Added Cl⁻ produce slight acceleration in rates. Thus, the

Fig. 1. Bunnett 'ω' plots for the hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA in 20% (v/v) dioxane-water at 55 °C : (•) H₂SO₄, (■) HCl, (▲) HClO₄.

Fig. 2. Bunnett-Olsen 'φ' plots for the hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA in 20% (v/v) dioxane-water at 55 °C : (•) H₂SO₄, (■) HCl, (▲) HClO₄.

Fig. 3. Cox-Yates excess acidity plots for the hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA in 20% (v/v) dioxane-water at 55 °C : (•) H₂SO₄, (■) HCl, (▲) HClO₄.

data in Table 4 suggest that the substrate is undergoing reaction by an A-2 pathway.

Solvent effect : The hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA was measured by varying percentage of co-solvents from 10–70% (v/v) in 2.9 M HCl at 55 °C. The results are listed in Table 5, show that the rate constant of the hydrolysis reaction is sensitive to solvent composition. In DMSO, the rate constant increases with increasing solvent composition. In dioxane, acetonitrile, acetone and ethanol rate constants decreases with the increasing solvent composition.

The interpretation of the kinetic solvent effect on

Table 4. Effect of salt on the hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA in 20% (v/v) dioxane-water at 55 °C

Salt [M]	$k_{\psi} \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹) HCl (1.45 M)		
	LiCl	NaCl	KCl
nil	5.9	5.9	5.9
0.5	8.2	13.3	12.2
1.0	8.8	17.8	12.9
1.5	6.9	15.2	8.9
2.0	5.3	12.7	10.9

Table 5. Effect of different solvents on hydrolysis of *p*-CIPFHA at 55 °C with 2.9 M HCl

Solvent % (v/v)	$k_{\psi} \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹)				
	Dioxane	DMSO	Acetonitrile	Acetone	Ethanol
10	24.0	23.3	14.5	16.9	16.1
20	21.2	27.5	12.9	15.2	11.5
40	20.6	33.8	8.8	8.2	10.2
60	14.7	22.2	7.3	5.9	9.2
70	13.5	17.9	4.3	–	7.3

reaction rates is difficult and is, in general, dominated more by exceptions than rules. How a particular solvent will effect each step in a reaction is hard to predict since what is observed experimentally is the net effect. No simple theory appears adequate to explain the effects observed.

On the basis of above discussion and results obtained from Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen and excess acidity analysis the most plausible mechanism (Scheme 1) appears to involve a rapid protonation of *p*-chlorophenyl-2-furohydroxamic acid, followed by a slow reaction of water with *O*-protonated form, (1), leading to the transition complex, (2), and subsequent hydrolysis resulting in the

Scheme 1

fission of *N*-acylbond giving corresponding carboxylic acid, (3), and protonated hydroxylamine, (4), as the products.

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